

Second Language Immersion Experience

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What connections were you able to make with the content of the movie, and why do you believe that you were able to make these connections?

The movie selected is *Viva Maria* 1965. In the beginning, audio in French language made it difficult to understand what the film is about. Audio and visuals helped to understand that the film is about the war. With the visual, understanding of the release timings of the movie, it appeared that a man was trying to use a little girl to explode many places. The video of the film appeared as if the actress (Bridget Bardot) is trying to escape. She was disguised as boy and she hides in a circus van. Still many things were not clear and it was difficult to make connection with certain things. Watching the film with English subtitles helped to understand and connect visuals, audio, and video with the content. This experience clearly helped to understand that language play an important role in understanding the real idea and content. In the beginning, misunderstanding about the man who used little girl for many explosions, became clear with the English subtitles that the man was actually little girl's father. They were fighting for the revolutionary cause. This experience also helped me to connect the content of the movie with the French revolution.

How was your understanding influenced during each of the 15 minute stages added?

Every fifteen minutes of the movie changed my understanding of the film. In the early fifteen minutes, it was difficult for me to understand anything with the audio. Second 15 minutes of audio and visuals were also difficult as it was not easy to understand things only with visuals developed the understanding that two girls work in the theatre. Third 15 minutes with audio and video input made it clear that the girls worked in Circus Company, but they encountered with some revolutionists. Video made it easier for me to understand and connect

things. The next fifteen minutes with subtitles made it clear that the girls and crew of Circus Company were imprisoned.

Language Acquisition Theoretical Principles Relevant Through this Experience

Many theories support the idea that first language and other communication measures help to develop better understanding about the content. For example, Krashen's theory of language acquisition is relevant through this experience, "Acquisition requires meaningful interaction in the target language - natural communication - in which speakers are concerned not with the form of their utterances but with the messages they are conveying and understanding." (Krashen quoted by Cooke, 2007, p.224).

Level of language proficiency need to effectively follow the story, and the best way to acquire such a level

With the video, it is not required to develop very high language proficiency. Video and subtitles help to understand the whole story. Even without subtitles, it is easy to follow the story, but without video and without any visual, it is very difficult to understand the story only with the audio. Understanding story only with the help of audio requires high level of language proficiency.

How would your understanding be different if you did not have a literacy base in your first language?

It was not possible to connect the previous visuals and idea of the story without literacy in first language. Subtitles in English helped to develop better understanding about the movie and it even helped to understand about rest of the movie.

References

Cooke, L. W. (Ed.). (2007). *Frontiers in higher education*. Nova Publishers.

<https://books.google.com/books?id=JzyOkFiMN6IC&printsec=frontcover>

Viva Maria (1965). <http://www.imdb.com/title/tt0059956/>